

Local Government in Poland

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

Andżelika Mirska

University of Warsaw

Partners

Eurac Research
Institute for Comparative Federalism
Italy

LMU Munich
Research Center for Public Procurement
Law and Administrative Cooperations
Germany

Autonomous University of Madrid
Institute of Local Law
Spain

Institut für Föderalismus
Institut du Fédéralisme
Institute of Federalism

University of Fribourg
Institute of Federalism
Switzerland

NALAS
Network of Associations of Local
Authorities of South East Europe
France

ximpulse
Ximpulse GmbH
Switzerland

KDZ
Center for Public Administration Research
Austria

Council of Europe
Congress of Local and Regional Authorities
France

Faculty of Political Science
and International Studies
University of Warsaw

University of Warsaw
Institute of Political Science
Poland

ZELS
Association of the Units of Local Self-Government
North Macedonia

University of the Western Cape
Dullah Omar Institute for Constitutional
Law, Governance and Human Rights
South Africa

Addis Ababa University
Center for Federalism and Governance Studies
Ethiopia

UNIVERSIDAD
NACIONAL DE
SAN MARTÍN

Universidad Nacional de General San Martín
School of Politics and Government
Argentina

SALGA
South African Local Government Association
South Africa

जवाहरलाल नेहरू विश्वविद्यालय
Jawaharlal Nehru University

Jawaharlal Nehru University
India

University of Technology Sydney
Institute for Public Policy and Governance
Centre for Local Government
Australia

National University of Singapore
Centre for Asian Legal Studies
Asia Pacific Centre for Environmental Law
Singapore

University of Western Ontario
Centre for Urban Policy and Local Governance
Canada

November 2021

The Country Report on Local Government in Poland is a product of the LoGov-project: “Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay”.

The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

LICENSE

CC BY 4.0

INFORMATION

Eurac Research
Viale Druso/Drususallee, 1
39100 Bolzano/Bozen – Italy

logov@eurac.edu
www.logov-rise.eu

SCIENTIFIC COORDINATION

Eurac Research: Karl Kössler

WP 1 – Local Responsibilities and Public Services

LMU Munich: Martin Burgi

WP 2 – Local Financial Arrangements

Universidad Autónoma de Madrid: Francisco Velasco Caballero

WP 3 – Structure of Local Government

University of Fribourg: Eva Maria Belser

WP 4 – Intergovernmental Relations of Local Government

NALAS – Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South East Europe: Elton Stafa

WP 5 – People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making

Ximpulse GmbH: Erika Schläppi

EDITORIAL TEAM

University of Warsaw: Andželika Mirska
Eurac Research: Karl Kössler, Theresia Morandell, Caterina Salvo, Annika Kress, Petra Malferttheiner

GRAPHIC DESIGN

Eurac Research: Alessandra Stefanut

COVER PHOTO

Adam Nieścioruk/Unsplash

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 823961.

Contents

1. The System of Local Government in Poland.....	3
2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in Poland: An Introduction	12
2.2. <i>The Provision of Local Public Transport</i>	15
2.3. <i>Provision of Internet Infrastructure by Local Government: A Step Towards Smart Villages</i>	18
2.4. <i>Lack of Effective Housing Management in Communes and Attempts to Recover from the Crisis</i> ... 25	
3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in Poland: An Introduction	32
3.2. <i>Investment Expenditure of Local Governments: The Role of European Funds in the Financial Strategies of Rural gminas</i>	42
3.3. <i>Integrated Territorial Investment (ITI)</i>	46
3.4. <i>The Importance of the ‘Village Fund’ for the Mobilization of Rural Residents to Civic Participation</i>	50
4.1. The Structure of Local Government in Poland: An Introduction	56
4.2. <i>What does Metropolitan Cooperation in the Functional Area of the Capital Warsaw Involve?</i>	62
4.3. <i>First Territorial Unit of Metropolitan Nature in Poland: The Metropolitan Union ‘Upper Silesian-Zagłębie Metropolis’</i>	67
4.4. <i>The Association ‘Gdansk-Gdynia-Sopot Metropolitan Area’ as an Example of Urban–Rural Cooperation</i>	75
5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Poland: An Introduction.....	83
5.2. <i>Institutionalizing Intergovernmental Relations in Poland: The Joint Commission of the Government and Territorial Self-Government</i>	85
5.3. <i>County-Commune Unions as a New Form of Intergovernmental Relations in Poland: The Beskidian County and Commune Union</i>	88
5.4. <i>The Interface between Subnational and National Levels of Government: The Role of National Local Self-government Organizations</i>	94
6.1. People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making in Poland: An Introduction	102
6.2. <i>Decisions on Expanding the City Territory at the Expense of the Rural Area: Consultations with Residents or a Local Referendum?</i>	106
6.3. <i>Youth Commune Council in Poland</i>	115
6.4. <i>Participatory Fund in Cities</i>	120

Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments

5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Poland: An Introduction

Andżelika Mirska, *University of Warsaw*

The model of a unitary state, adopted by Poland, assumes that the legislature is undivided – it is wielded only by the Polish Parliament (two chambers: Sejm and Senate). The principle of administrative decentralization means a division of the executive. It is wielded by the authorities of the Polish state (the President of the Republic of Poland and the government - The Council of Ministers of the Republic of Poland with the central government that is centralized and subject to the governance of the government). The local government has functioned within the executive since 1990. It has fulfilled a part of the tasks of the executive, but it is not subject hierarchically to the government. The local government (in Poland: territorial self-government) is independent in its activities undertaken for the good of its members (residents). However, its activities cannot violate the law (the Constitution of the Republic of Poland, acts, regulation, the EU law). Legal supervision is a mechanism which is triggered when the law is violated by local government (there is no difference with regard to urban and rural municipalities). Supervision is exercised only by the authorities of the Polish state. The local government may challenge that supervision through a complaint lodged to an administrative court. Ultimately, therefore, the court settles the dispute between the state and local government (Article 166 of the Constitution of the Republic of Poland of 1997: ‘The administrative courts shall settle jurisdictional disputes between units of local government and units of government administration’).

However, there are no governance dependencies or supervision relations between three levels of territorial self-government (*gminy, powiats, voivodeship*). Therefore, the relations between local governments are always voluntary and mutually agreed (only exceptions include situation relating to public security as well as unusual and emergency situations – which are precisely determined in the act).

The state-local government relations are manifold. On the one hand, the local government is subject to the state's regulations and supervision. The scope of tasks and financial resources are regulated by the act – the local government must submit to them. On the other hand, the Preamble of the Constitution of the Republic of Poland includes the principle of cooperation between the public authorities, therefore, between the government and local government as well – for the common good. The principle of cooperation between the authorities, referred to in the Preamble, corresponds with the multi-level governance structure, well established in the modern science of public governance.

In the democratic state there are various mechanisms in place to enable the participation in the law-making process. With regard to the local government, the Joint Commission of the

Government and Territorial Self-Government (*Komisja Wspólna Rządu i Samorządu Terytorialnego*) has functioned in Poland since 1993. It is 'the forum for the elaboration of a joint position of the central government and local government'. The local governments are formed by the representatives of all-Poland organizations of local government units, both representing the interests of urban and rural municipalities, including metropolises.

The Polish law guarantees the *gminas*, *powiats* and voivodeship the right to establish associations. Their objective should be to support the idea of local government and to defend their common interests. These associations can be established by the units of one local government level, but they can also include the units of different levels. The Association of Polish Local Governments (*gminas*, *powiats*, voivodeships) is such an association established in 2017. The association refers to the Christian values what is novel among the all-Poland associations which do not declare a worldview orientation in their statutes.

The primary role is played by 6 all-Poland local government organizations: the Union of Polish Metropolises (*Unia Metropolii Polskich*); the Union of Small Polish Towns (*Unia Miasteczek Polskich*); the Association of Polish Cities (*Związek Miast Polskich*); the Association of Rural Communes of the Republic of Poland (*Związek Gmin Wiejskich Rzeczypospolitej Polskiej*); the Association of Polish Powiats (*Związek Powiatów Polskich*); the Association of Voivodeships of the Republic of Poland (*Związek Województw Rzeczypospolitej Polskiej*).

There is a range of examples of associations of a regional or even local nature (e.g. the Association of Communes and Powiats of Małopolska (*Stowarzyszenie Gmin i Powiatów Małopolski*), the Association of Communes and Powiats of Central Pomerania (*Stowarzyszenie Gmin i Powiatów Pomorza Środkowego*). There are also associations which determined their scope of interest, e.g.: the Masovian Association of Communes for the Development of Information Society (*Mazowieckie Stowarzyszenie Gmin na Rzecz Rozwoju Społeczeństwa Informacyjnego*), the Association of Health Resort Communes of the Republic of Poland (*Stowarzyszenie Gmin Uzdrowiskowych RP*).

All associations are subject to the registration in the court (the entry to the National Court Register) and legal supervision by the state.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Website of the Association of Polish Cities, <<http://www.miasta.pl/en>>

Website of the Association of Voivodeships the Republic of Poland, <<https://zwrp.pl/en/>>

Website of the Joint Commission of Government and Territorial Self Government, <<http://kwrist.mswia.gov.pl>>

Website of the Union of Polish Metropolises, <<https://www.metropolie.pl/en/>>

Contacts

Local Government and the Changing
Urban-Rural Interplay
www.logov-rise.eu
logov@eurac.edu

This project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020 re-
search and innovation programme under
grant agreement No 823961.

